

The 1st Forum of the Academy of Medical Sciences of the Serbian Medical Society

The Academy of Medical Sciences of the Serbian Medical Society (Academy) gathers our most famous scientists and experts from various fields of medicine and dentistry. During the 46 years of its activity, the Academy has held over 850 scientific and educational meetings, a large number of lecture cycles for the general population at the Ilija M. Kolarac Endowment, it has published dozens of monographs and thus contributed to the promotion of the scientific and professional work of distinguished members of the Academy, as well as to the education of doctors and the popularization of science.

On March 24, 2023, the Academy will organize the *1st Forum of the Academy of Medical Sciences of the Serbian Medical Society*. It will be a scientific meeting where the research results of the members of the Academy and their coworkers will be presented and discussed with the aim of promoting their scientific work and realizing their better cooperation in subsequent studies. The topic of the *1st Forum of the Academy* is "Prevention, Diagnosis, Treatment and Control of Mass Infectious and Non-Infectious Diseases." It has been our opinion that such a broad topic would attract experts from various fields and thus illustrate the wide-ranging field of scientific interest and work of the Academy members.

Twenty-four papers have been submitted for the *1st Forum of the Academy*. The greatest attention is paid to COVID-19. The results and experiences of the clinical presentation, course, treatment, and outcome of the disease are presented, as well as the results of experimental research and presentations of various post-COVID disorders. These results and experiences are valuable guideposts for planning measures in future epidemics that infectologists and epidemiologists have been warning us about.

In addition to COVID-19, lectures will also be delivered on some important infectious diseases that are not given enough attention, and which can seriously threaten health and life. These are, above all, tuberculosis and fungal diseases, which will be discussed by our well-known experts.

The meeting dedicated to mass diseases could not but include lectures on malignant diseases. Significant results of the study of modern drugs will be presented, as well as research of insufficiently studied tumors that require additional education of doctors, especially concerning the diagnosis of these diseases.

At the Forum, there will be an opportunity to find out the results of clinical and experimental studies on cardiovascular diseases, such as pharmacogenetic studies and analyses of the results of modern methods of cardiovascular diseases treatment.

Studies from the field of dentistry confirm that modern research requires a multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary approach, which has made it possible to achieve exceptional progress in the treatment of oral and dental diseases.

In addition to the presentation from the aforementioned fields, results from ophthalmology, anesthesiology, and otorhinolaryngology will also be presented. The wide range of topics and the quality of submitted abstracts confirm that Academy members contribute significantly to professional and scientific work and the continuous progress of all fields of medicine.

We hope that at the *1st Forum of the Academy*, doctors from different specialties, as well as experts from other related fields, will gather and that a lively discussion will contribute to the quality of the meeting. We wish to all the participants that the Forum fulfills the expectations of us all – the organizers, the authors of the presented studies, and the audience – and that it will be an incentive for the Academy Forum to become a regular annual scientific meeting of the Academy.

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Women's oral health as a public health indicator (Case Study Serbia)

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Introduction/Objective Prevalence of oral diseases is over 90% and gender also plays an important role. Women show better preventive behavior in oral health than men, but their dentition is often incomplete.

The aim of this study was to examine the state of women's oral health in Vojvodina and the use of dental health care (demographic, socio-economic determinants, dental anxiety) to assess the impact of oral health on women's quality of life.

Methods The research was conducted as an epidemiological cross-sectional study. Questionnaires: on general and dental health status, on the impact of oral health on quality of life (OHIP-14), for the assessment of dental anxiety (DAS), and the Modified Oral Health Assessment Form for Adults of the World Health Organization, were used.

Results 1900 women aged 16 years and over were included. The results showed that the better dental and periodontal status of women was negatively correlated with age ($t=24,242$; $p=0,000$) and positively correlated with education (χ^2 test; $\chi^2=70,919$; $p=0,000$), material condition (χ^2 test; $\chi^2=67,716$; $p=0,000$) and employment status (χ^2 test; $\chi^2=30,630$; $p=0,000$). The most important predictors of good oral health of women were a high level of education and financial status, employment, the existence of partners and social support. The coverage of women with regular dental examinations was less than 20%.

Conclusion This research confirmed the public health importance of women's oral health. Our results are useful for future research and the creation of programs for prevention of oral diseases and improvement of oral health in women.

Keywords: oral health; women; public health

Conflict of interest: None declared.

Subacute thyroiditis (De Quervain) during the COVID-19 pandemic

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Introduction/Objective Dysfunction of the thyroid gland, usually transient, was observed in approximately 15% of patients with mild to moderate symptoms of COVID-19 since the receptor for ACE2, used by SARS-CoV-2 virion for cell entry, is highly expressed in thyroid tissue. Subacute thyroiditis (SAT) is an inflammatory disorder of the thyroid gland associated with viral infection (direct viral toxicity or an inflammatory response to the virus): mumps, measles, rubella, coxsackie, and adenoviruses. There is increasing evidence that SARS-CoV-2 can also be considered responsible for causing subacute and atypical thyroiditis. The aim of the study was to analyze the effect of COVID-19 infection on appearance and disease course of SAT.

Methods In the period 2006–2021, a total of 66 patients were treated for SAT at our clinic. During the COVID-19 pandemic (years 2020 and 2021), seven new patients with SAT were presented. In year 2022 no new patients were registered at our clinic. The diagnosis was made on the basis of the anamnesis (pain in the neck and thyroid gland), high erythrocyte sedimentation rate and CRP, ultrasound, and occasionally thyroid aspiration cytology (epithelioid cell findings).

Results In four out of seven patients who previously had COVID-19, SAT had an atypical course: two patients had normal ultrasound findings, one patient had anamnesis of a painful neck, while the palpation findings during the ultrasound examination of the thyroid gland were normal, and one suffered a relapse of SAT after five years.

Conclusion SAT after SARS-CoV-2 infection has presented an atypical course in four out of seven patients treated at our institution. More investigation is required in order to associate the atypical course of SAT with SARS-CoV-2 infection.

Keywords: COVID-19; thyroid gland; subacute thyroiditis; SARS-CoV-2 infection

Conflict of interest: None declared.